

On Forecasting Truck Driving Manoeuvres with Foundation Models for Time Series Data (Supplementary Materials¹)

Beatriz Cabrero-Daniel¹, Simon Börjesson², Erik Ersmark², Pierre Nugues², Klara Eliasson³, Christian Berger⁴

¹Department of Communication, Quality Management and Information Systems, Mid Sweden University, Östersund, Sweden, ²Department of Computer Science, Lund University, Lund, Sweden, ³Volvo Group Trucks Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden, and ⁴Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Gothenburg and Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden

Table I

UNIVARIATE FORECASTING OF THE SIGNALS `CONSTANT_1`, `LINEAR_1`, AND `SINUSOID_1`. THE FOUNDATION MODELS WERE ALSO FINE-TUNED WITH DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES. THE BEST RESULTS FOR EACH SIGNAL ARE IN **BOLD** AND THE SECOND BEST ARE UNDERLINED.

Model	Setting	Prediction length = 25			Prediction length = 50		
		constant_1	linear_1	sinusoid_1	constant_1	linear_1	sinusoid_1
Chronos-Bolt (Tiny)	Zero-shot	0.000	0.006	1.302	0.000	0.008	1.296
	Full FT	0.000	0.008	0.089	0.000	0.006	0.091
	LoRA FT*	0.020	0.004	0.101	0.019	0.005	0.103
Chronos-Bolt (Mini)	Zero-shot	0.000	0.012	1.136	0.000	0.013	1.188
	Full FT	0.000	0.006	0.081	0.000	0.006	0.078
	LoRA FT*	<u>0.008</u>	0.003	0.099	<u>0.011</u>	0.004	0.098
Chronos-Bolt (Small)	Zero-shot	0.000	0.004	1.305	0.000	0.004	1.405
	Full FT	0.000	0.004	0.066	0.000	0.003	0.065
	LoRA FT*	0.014	0.004	0.067	0.014	0.004	0.071
Chronos-Bolt (Base)	Zero-shot	0.000	<u>0.002</u>	0.993	0.000	0.005	1.906
	Full FT	0.000	<u>0.002</u>	0.053	0.000	<u>0.002</u>	0.051
	LoRA FT*	0.011	0.005	0.055	0.012	0.005	0.056
Moirai (Small)	Zero-shot	0.000	0.011	2.902	0.000	0.060	2.903
	Full FT	0.000	0.786	2.127	0.000	0.851	2.128
Moirai (Base)	Zero-shot	0.000	0.010	2.426	0.000	0.014	2.376
	Full FT	0.000	0.788	2.127	0.000	0.853	2.128
Moirai (Large)	Zero-shot	0.000	0.006	2.015	0.000	0.026	2.124
	Full FT	0.000	0.864	2.139	0.000	0.928	2.136
PatchTST	From scratch	0.026	0.746	0.009	0.022	0.685	0.009
TFT	From scratch	0.000	0.001	<u>0.011</u>	0.000	0.001	<u>0.010</u>
AutoARIMA	From scratch	0.000	0.074	7.460	0.000	0.147	9.103

Table II

*

*: Our LoRA implementation for Chronos-Bolt was done in AutoGluon 1.2.0, but the rest of the Chronos tests were run in AutoGluon 1.3.0, when a fix to constant signals was applied (see pull requests in the chronos-forecasting and autogluon libraries). This explains why LoRA FT led to worse performance on the `constant_1` signal.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research (SSF), Grant Number FUS21-0004 SAICOM, Swedish Research Council (VR) under grant agreements 2021-04533 and 2023-03810, Vinnova project 2024-01568 within the Advanced Digitalization program, and the Wallenberg AI, Autonomous Systems and Software Program (WASP) funded by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation.

¹Access: 10.5281/zenodo.20135253

Table III
 UNIVARIATE (UNIV.) AND MULTIVARIATE (MULTIV.) FORECASTING OF THE SIGNALS *steering wheel angle* AND *longitudinal acceleration*. THE FOUNDATION MODELS WERE ALSO FINE-TUNED WITH DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES. THE BEST RESULTS ARE IN **BOLD** AND THE SECOND BEST ARE UNDERLINED. A ‘-’ MEANS THE MODEL DOES NOT SUPPORT MULTIVARIATE FORECASTING.

Model	Setting	Prediction length = 25				Prediction length = 50			
		steeringwheelangle		acceleration_x		steeringwheelangle		acceleration_x	
		Univ.	Multiv.	Univ.	Multiv.	Univ.	Multiv.	Univ.	Multiv.
Chronos-Bolt (Tiny)	Zero-shot	1.075	–	0.248	,	1.624	–	0.303	,
	Full FT	0.492	–	0.205	,	0.562	–	0.246	,
	LoRA FT	0.396	–	0.189	,	0.405	–	0.226	,
Chronos-Bolt (Mini)	Zero-shot	1.146	–	0.247	,	1.699	–	0.303	,
	Full FT	0.444	–	0.201	,	0.481	–	0.242	,
	LoRA FT	0.399	–	0.185	,	0.386	–	0.219	,
Chronos-Bolt (Small)	Zero-shot	1.060	–	0.247	,	1.643	–	0.301	,
	Full FT	0.409	–	0.197	,	0.478	–	0.235	,
	LoRA FT	0.370	–	0.186	,	0.374	–	0.227	,
Chronos-Bolt (Base)	Zero-shot	0.978	–	0.248	,	1.511	–	0.307	,
	Full FT	0.411	–	0.196	,	0.418	–	0.233	,
	LoRA FT	0.349	–	0.186	,	<u>0.357</u>	–	<u>0.224</u>	,
Moirai (Small)	Zero-shot	1.540	1.494	0.269	0.263	2.258	2.167	0.338	0.336
	Full FT	1.259	1.296	0.250	0.214	1.406	1.274	0.293	0.262
Moirai (Base)	Zero-shot	1.322	1.290	0.268	0.280	2.097	2.052	0.334	0.361
	Full FT	1.573	1.569	0.346	0.428	1.723	1.438	0.361	0.418
Moirai (Large)	Zero-shot	1.218	1.195	0.255	0.270	1.920	1.923	0.330	0.347
	Full FT	1.572	1.533	0.270	0.348	1.498	1.589	0.323	0.388
PatchTST	From scratch	<u>0.362</u>	0.374	<u>0.184</u>	0.186	0.345	0.358	0.226	0.227
TFT	From scratch	0.453	0.411	0.219	0.171	0.437	0.400	0.259	0.225
AutoARIMA	From scratch	1.106	–	0.259	,	1.930	–	0.326	–